

Formidlingsaktivitet

Art: STEM/STEAM science communication.

Sted: Nyborg Gymnasium / IB

Skole: Nyborg Gymnasium / IB, 1.i & 2.i & 3.i elever

Dato: 14. march 2024.

Tid: 15:15 – 17:30.

Antal elever: ca. 13 students (group-picture was taken too late ...)

GDPR / pictures for public? Yes. Permission obtained.

Lærerkontakt: Kurt Strickertsson

Formidler: Mattias Ermakov Thing (Syddansk Universitet, FKF / SDU-Galaxy).

